

**STUDY OF GENETIC POLYMORPHISM OF VDR TNF GENES IN THE
UZBEK POPULATION OF THE SAMARKAND REGION**

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As part of this study, the nature of the distribution of alleles and genotypes of the polymorphic variant of the vitamin D receptor gene BsmI rs1544410 was studied in 64 patients with type 1 diabetes, in individuals of the Uzbek population living in Samarkand.

When analyzing the results obtained as part of genotyping, it was revealed that allele A was found more often in the group of patients compared to the control group by 1.64 times, with indicators $OR=1.978$, $95\%CI=1.091 >1.978> 3.585$, $\chi^2=5.13$ ($p=0.02$). Allele G was more common in the group of healthy individuals, with $OR=0.506$, $95\%CI=0.279 >0.506>0.917$, $\chi^2=5.13$ ($p=0.02$). When analyzing genotypes, the homozygous genotype GG of the vitamin D receptor gene BsmI rs1544410 showed significant differences in the frequency of occurrence, since this genotype was 1.5 times more common in the group of practically healthy individuals with indicators $OR = 0.429$, $95\%CI = 0.204 >0.429 > 0.902$, $\chi^2=5.062$ ($p=0.024451$). For the heterozygous genotype GA and homozygous genotype AA of the vitamin D receptor gene BsmI rs1544410, no significant differences were found in this sample.

Thus, in this sample, when studying the nature of the distribution of alleles and genotypes of the vitamin D receptor gene BsmI rs1544410, the protective allele G and the protective genotype GGa were significant, as well as the allele A, which is a significant predisposing marker, however, genotypes with the presence of this allele did not reach their true significance in this sample.

The TNFA gene is located on chromosome 6 on its short arm in the p21.3 region and contains 4 exons. There is evidence of the relationship between TNFA

gene polymorphism and the amount of its production. Scientists have identified several SNPs of the TNFA gene: -1031T/C, -863C/A and -857C/A, -308G/A and -238G/A. Among them, two polymorphic variants of the TNFA gene are the most studied: -238G/A -308G/A, which have multidirectional effects on the production of this cytokine: at position -308, the replacement of guanine with adenine promotes an increase in the production of the TNFA cytokine, and at point -238 it leads to a decrease.

In a comparative study of the distribution of allele frequencies and genotypes of polymorphic markers of the TNF α -308G/A gene in groups of patients with type 1 diabetes, in individuals of the Uzbek population living in Samarkand and in controls (Table 2), a statistically significant increase in the frequency of the A allele in patients with compared with the control group (12.5% and 6.57%, respectively; OR = 2.033; 95% CI: 1.053 > 2.033 > 3.924; $\chi^2 = 4.62$ ($p = 0.03$)). The G allele of the studied polymorphism was found significantly less frequently compared to the control group (87.5% and 93.43%, respectively; OR = 0.492; 95% CI: 0.255 > 0.492 > 0.949; $\chi^2 = 4.62$ ($p = 0.031593$))

A comparative analysis of TNF α -308G/A genotypes in the distribution of GG genotypes revealed significant differences between patients with type 1 diabetes in the Uzbek population living in Samarkand and the control group (75.0% and 86.87%, respectively; OR = 0.453; 95% CI: 0.225 > 0.453 > 0.913; $\chi^2 = 5.062$). When analyzing the heterozygous GA genotype, differences were identified between the frequency of occurrence in patients and the control group (25.0% and 13.13%, respectively; OR = 2.205; 95% CI: 1.095 > 2.205 > 4.441; $\chi^2 = 5.062$). As already described above, a significant difference was found in the frequency of occurrence of allele A, the studied polymorphism TNF α -308G/A, but the genotypic analysis of the homozygous AA genotype was not registered.

The data obtained indicate that the -308(G/A) TNF polymorphism makes a significant contribution to the susceptibility to the disease and is a significant

prognosis factor in patients with type 1 diabetes in the Uzbek population living in Samarkand.

References:

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